

DEVELOPMENT OF PROFESSIONAL COMPETENCE USING DIGITAL TECHNOLOGIES

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ABSTRACT

the article discusses the dependence of professional competencies on personal qualities, professional knowledge, skills, abilities and experience, as well as the role of digital technologies in the development of professional competencies.

With the growing influence of digital technologies, and especially the Internet, the debate about their impact is getting louder: are they a boon for humanity, providing unlimited opportunities for communication and trade, education and free expression, or a threat to our way of life, undermining social structures and even the political system and posing a danger to our well-being?

Digital technologies can create economic prospects by providing vocational training and career guidance services for young people and by creating new types of work.

Acceleration of the educational process, in addition to information and communication technologies (ICT) in the field of education, should be supported by teacher training and effective pedagogical activity.

In the message of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Shavkat Mirziyoyev to the Oliy Majlis dated

December 29, 2020, he stressed "In order to radically improve the quality of education, first of all it is necessary to bring curricula, teaching aids for teachers in line with advanced international standards."

Professional competencies are the ability to perform professional duties or perform a specific professional task. That is, it is assumed that you will be able to perform the work efficiently and get the desired result. Activity competence indicates that you have full-fledged knowledge and experience that will help you fulfill your work responsibilities.

Competence management is the practice of identifying the key skills necessary for an employee to achieve the results of a specific task, as well as developing and optimizing these skills in such a way that they best match the business strategy of the organization.

Professional competencies show the employer our abilities and advantages. Every time we are looking for a new job or

applying for a new position, we are faced with an assessment of our competencies. Professional competencies show the employer our abilities and advantages. Every time we are looking for a new job or applying for a new position, we are faced with an assessment of our competencies.

Here are some examples of professional competencies.

A set of professional qualities of a manager:

- Observation
- Conflict resolution
- Emotional intelligence
- Communication skills
- Production management
- Conversational skills
- Team building
- Delegation

Main professional competencies:

1. Teamwork
2. Responsibility
3. Business Awareness
4. Decision making
5. Communication
6. Leadership
7. Reliability and ethics
8. Focus on the results
9. Problem solving
10. Organizational skills

Therefore, according to the research of American specialists in the field of labor psychology, when developing professional competencies, it is necessary to pay attention to the personal qualities of a person, which is defined by the abbreviation CSAO:

- knowledge;
- skills;
- abilities;
- other qualities. Each professional competence can be described using specific

indicators. They represent standards of human behavior.

So, if the "personal" approach is "how?" (with which resources and which people you can work well), then "functionally" is "what?" (to what extent and in what capacity an employee should perform professional actions (functions)).

The "functional" approach is not taken into account, as a result of which it turns out: the experience or knowledge, abilities or motivation of the employee — the main thing is that the work is done at the proper level. The number of supporters of the functional approach is growing. And in modern practice, the term "professional skill" is often understood as the ability of the subject of professional activity to perform tasks in accordance with established standards.

Thus, professional competence is the ability of an employee to perform work in accordance with the requirements of the workplace and the requirements of the position – these are the tasks accepted in the organization or industry and the standards for their implementation.

Knowledge, skills, qualifications, experience, values acquired by a person in the process of education, act as an integral quality of competence and at the same time potential competence.

Depending on the manifestation of skills, experience and other qualities underlying the skills, we can include them in the competencies resulting from their use in a really specific situation in which we are competent.

Digital technologies cover many areas, and one of the main directions is the development of the labor market by changing the requirements for the professional skills of workers of different

professions. The main reason for this is "technological progress, as a result of which machines, not people, can perform more tasks. To solve this problem, we need a tool for forming a set of knowledge necessary for effective work in the digital economy."

Many information resources are already available online and offline. Thus, in order to obtain the necessary competencies, it is necessary to pay for available online platforms, including the world's leading universities (www.coursera.org ; www.edx.org; www.skillswise.com and others) in different directions. specializations and directions, and you can take advantage of free training courses.

Offline Learning you can find many different educational institutions offering different learning formats anywhere in the

world. On the one hand, the digital economy is changing and the labor market and qualification requirements for employees continue to change, on the other hand, the number of employees is increasing in conditions of constant uncertainty about their future. Too many different media to study will not allow you to achieve the desired result. The solution to these problems is the professional development of an employee within the framework of an individual development trajectory using a digital platform.

Thus, we can say that in the conditions of ongoing changes related to digital transformation, the development of professional competencies will ensure timely provision both in the labor market and in the field of vocational education and training for the new economy.

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